

Using Factorial Experiments For Calibration and Validation When Only Aggregated Effects Are Published

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Abstract

Process-based ecosystem models are often calibrated and validated against the results of factorial experiments, yet many published studies report only treatment main effects, omitting the full results for each treatment combination. Because the results are not available for each treatment combination, model validation and calibration often target main effects that averages over multiple actual treatments. This means that the model is simulating an experimental design that did not actually occur. Furthermore, treatment combinations can be non-additive even if the interaction is not statistically significant. This abstraction introduces additional error.

Here I present a method that enables calibration and validation against main effects by first simulating each treatment in the factorial experimental design, and then simulating the statistical analysis used to calculate the reported main effects. This method provides a more flexible and correct [wc?] approach to model-data comparison that accounts for interactions. This approach expands the usable experimental results for calibration/validation, reduces uncertainty compared to ignoring interactions, and provides a general framework for incorporating available data.

Introduction

Factorial experiments provide a foundation for agricultural and ecological research. These experiments evaluate how multiple factors and their interactions influence ecosystem processes. Although these experiments are designed to test specific hypotheses, they commonly used for calibrating and validating process-based models.

However, using these data presents challenges. Because these experiments were not designed to support model calibration and validation, they often omit key information that is required to reconstruct and simulate the system. For example,

because the focus is on the experimental treatments, the common factors not under investigation - like irrigation, planting date, fertilization rate - are not always reported. Another key challenge is how the results are reported. If the treatment interactions are not statistically significant, it is common practice to only report the main effects. Here we address a key challenge of how to simulate these aggregated ‘main’ effects.

This reporting practice creates a disconnect between the experimental conditions and the data that is available for model calibration and validation.

Such an experiment has 16 treatment combinations (4x4). However, if only the main effects are reported, there are only 4 reported effects. A common approach is to infer (disaggregate) the treatment means from the main effects. However, this is an underdetermined problem unless we make the strong assumption that there are no interaction effects. This is described in the “Status Quo” section, below.

Ideally, the underlying data and statistical calculations would be provided alongside experimental results. But for the foreseeable future, we will need methods that are able to utilize the information that is available in a statistically coherent way.

This document addresses this challenge by presenting a flexible method using an approach that simulates the data-generating process. By simulating each treatment in a factorial design *and* the statistical analysis that produces main effects, this method allows modelers to more directly compare models to data.

Approach: Simulating Main Effects as Mean of Treatment Predictions

Consider an experiment for which the main effects from a factorial experiment are reported, but the treatment means are not.

Specifically lets take the simple case of a two factor experiment with n levels of factor 1 and m levels of factor 2. There are $n \times m$ treatments, but only $n + m$ main effects are reported.

This approach will simulate the each treatment and then estimate the main effects. This follows the philosophy of ‘simulating the data generating process’, i.e., simulating all of the steps that would have been taken to generate the results that are actually reported.

Importantly, this approach is **Generalizable** to a wide variety of scenarios.

For example, if a cross-year mean is reported, but the model runs at a daily time step, the modeler would need to decide which time in the model output to compare against the observation. Using the proposed approach, the modeler

would simulate each year and then calculate the mean across years to compare against the reported mean.

Forward Simulation Approach

Using the two-factor experimental design that we have just described:

- Factor 1 (A) has n levels.
- Factor 2 (B) has m levels.

The full treatment effects matrix is:

$$Y_{ij} = G + M_i + N_j + I_{ij}$$

where:

- G is the global mean,
- M_i is the main effect of factor 1 at level i ,
- N_j is the main effect of factor 2 at level j ,
- I_{ij} represents interactions between the two factors.

Since only the main effects (M_i and N_j) are reported, but not the interaction terms, directly recovering the full Y_{ij} matrix is not possible without a strong assumption that there is no interaction ($I = 0$).

Instead of attempting to recover the treatment effects, I propose:

1. Model Simulation

- Configure and run a model for each of the $n \times m$ treatment conditions.
- Store the full set of simulated treatment effects, Y_{ij}^{sim} .

2. Aggregation to Main Effects

- Compute the simulated main effects using the same formulas used to report main effects:

$$M_i^{\text{sim}} = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{j=1}^m Y_{ij}^{\text{sim}} - G$$

$$N_j^{\text{sim}} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n Y_{ij}^{\text{sim}} - G$$

3. Calibration and Validation Against Reported Main Effects

- Calibration:
 - Compare the simulated main effects ($M_i^{\text{sim}}, N_j^{\text{sim}}$) to the reported main effects ($M_i^{\text{obs}}, N_j^{\text{obs}}$).
- Validation:
 - Compare treatment differences associated with practice changes.

note: evaluate whether it is more appropriate to compare the model output to the response ratio ($\log(\frac{M_{\text{practice change}}}{M_{\text{baseline}}})$) than to the treatment difference ($M_{\text{practice change}} - M_{\text{baseline}}$)?

Implementation in R

Below is an R implementation demonstrating this approach:

```
# Define the global mean
G <- 25

# Define the uncentered main effects (as reported in the paper)
M_eff <- c(-1, -5, 1, 5) # Factor 1 main effects
N_eff <- c(-8, 4, -4, 8) # Factor 2 main effects

# Simulate full treatment effects using a hypothetical model
set.seed(42) # For reproducibility

# (adding random error)
error <- matrix(rnorm(16, mean = 0, sd = 1), nrow = 4)

Y_sim <- outer(M_eff, N_eff, "+") + G + error

# Compute simulated main effects using the same formulas as
# in the paper
M_sim <- rowMeans(Y_sim) - G
N_sim <- colMeans(Y_sim) - G

# Compare simulated main effects to the reported ones
comparison_M <- cbind(Reported = M_eff, Simulated = M_sim)
comparison_N <- cbind(Reported = N_eff, Simulated = N_sim)

# Display results
print(
  "Comparison of Reported and Simulated Main Effects for Factor 1:"
)

[1] "Comparison of Reported and Simulated Main Effects for Factor 1:"
print(comparison_M)

      Reported Simulated
[1,]      -1 -0.3988026
[2,]      -5 -5.2530814
[3,]       1  1.7615497
[4,]       5  5.8651998
```

```
print(
  "Comparison of Reported and Simulated Main Effects for Factor 2:"
)
```

```
[1] "Comparison of Reported and Simulated Main Effects for Factor 2:"
```

```
print(comparison_N)
```

```
      Reported Simulated
[1,]      -8 -7.549437
[2,]       4  4.428752
[3,]      -4 -2.613194
[4,]       8  7.708745
```

Justification For this approach

- **Avoids the underdetermined problem** of trying to reconstruct missing treatment effects.
- **Validates the model against reported main effects** rather than requiring assumptions that may be difficult to justify.

This approach provides a practical way to evaluate a model with experimental data while avoiding the limitations and assumptions associated with disaggregating treatment means.

This approach also highlights the need for scientists to follow best practices in reporting experimental results including sharing data - at least at the level of the experimental unit / replicate - along with metadata required to simulate the system and code used to generate analyses.

Limitations of this approach

Non-Independence of model-data comparisons: The fact that each main effect is composed of four treatment effects can lead to correlated estimates, which should be taken into account when interpreting results [Method TBD].

The Status Quo

There are a few common approaches to using main effects from factorial experiments for model calibration and validation.

One approach is to use the main effects directly. Another approach is to disaggregate treatment means from main effects. Both have limitations and are require strong assumptions.

Using the main effects directly requires a strong assumption that the main effects represent what would happen if the treatments were applied in isolation. This is unlikely to be true if the main effect is a composite of multiple treatment effects.

Disaggregating treatment means from main effects is an underdetermined problem unless we assume that there are no interaction effects.

We present two cases: first with interaction and then assuming no interaction effects, and then demonstrate that Case 1 is underdetermined and Case 2 works but only with strong assumptions.

To use one of these approaches it would be necessary to determine if one or both of these is a conservative assumption that reliably underestimates the treatment effect.

Case 0: Using Main Effects Directly

[TBD] relatively trivial.

Case 1: Disaggregation Assuming Interaction Effects

Assuming interaction effects - underdetermined

Let's define our variables:

- Y_{ij} represents the treatment effect when factor 1 is at level i and factor 2 is at level j
- M_i represents the main effect of factor 1 at level i
- N_j represents the main effect of factor 2 at level j
- G represents the grand mean across all treatments

The statistical model including main effects and interaction terms can be written as:

$$Y_{ij} = G + M_i + N_j + I_{ij}$$

Where I_{ij} is the interaction effect between the two factors.

For example, with $m = n = 4$ (4 levels of each factor), I have a 4×4 matrix of treatment effects:

$$Y = \begin{bmatrix} Y_{11} & Y_{12} & \cdot & \cdot \\ Y_{21} & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & Y_{44} \end{bmatrix}$$

The reported main effects are calculated as:

Factor 1 main effects:

$$M_i = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^m Y_{ij} - G, \quad i \in \{1 \dots m\}$$

Factor 2 main effects:

$$N_j = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^n Y_{ij} - G, \quad j \in \{1 \dots n\}$$

Where the grand mean G is:

$$G = \frac{1}{m \times n} \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n Y_{ij}$$

This gives us $m + n$ equations for $m \times n$ unknowns. When $m, n \geq 3$, the system is **underdetermined**, with infinite solutions.

Case 2: Additive Model Assuming No Interaction Effects

Assuming no interaction effects - works with strong assumptions

Note that the absence of a statistically significant interaction *is insufficient evidence* for the assumption that there are interaction effects because the experiment was not designed to test this.

If we assume that there are no interaction effects ($I_{ij} = 0$ for all i, j), the model simplifies to:

$$Y_{ij} = G + M_i + N_j$$

Under this additive model, treatment effects are uniquely determined by the reported main effects and the grand mean.

$$Y_{ij} = G + M_i + N_j \tag{1}$$

For our 4×4 example, this gives us:

$$\begin{aligned} Y_{11} &= G + M_1 + N_1 \\ Y_{12} &= G + M_1 + N_2 \\ Y_{13} &= G + M_1 + N_3 \\ &\vdots \\ Y_{44} &= G + M_4 + N_4 \end{aligned}$$

With this assumption, we can uniquely determine all treatment effects from the reported main effects and the grand mean.

Instructions for Estimating Y_{ij} (Case 2)

When we assume an additive model, the treatment effects Y_{ij} can be estimated from the reported main effects M_i and N_j as follows:

1. Compile reported main effects M_i and N_j .
2. Calculate the Grand Mean G as average of all main effects:

$$G = \frac{1}{n \times m} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m Y_{ij}$$

3. Calculate Main Effects (difference between treatment mean and grand mean):

- **Factor 1:** For each level i , the main effect is given by:

$$M_i = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{j=1}^m Y_{ij} - G$$

- **Factor 2:** For each level j , the main effect is given by:

$$N_j = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n Y_{ij} - G$$

4. Calculate mean for each treatment Y_{ij} :

$$Y_{ij} = G + M_i + N_j$$

5. Verify that the computed treatment means are consistent with the reported main effects by re-aggregating them:
 - For Factor 1: Check that the average of Y_{ij} across all levels j equals $G + M_i$.
 - For Factor 2: Check that the average of Y_{ij} across all levels i equals $G + N_j$.

Examples to Illustrate (and check) Case 1 and 2 Scenarios

Let's illustrate both cases with a simple example using R.

Variables

- **G:** Grand Mean
- **M, N:** Main effects of factors
- **Y:** Treatment matrix
- **I:** Interaction effects between factors

Subscripts

- **_eff:** "effect": deviation from the grand mean.
- **_mean:** Actual mean values (effect + grand mean) that are the values of interest.
- **_est:** Estimated reconstructed values.
- **_sim:** Simulated values
- **_int:** Represents values with interaction effects

Setup

```
# Define the global (grand) mean
G <- 25

# Define the uncentered main effects for factor 1 and factor 2
# (These are typically reported in the literature)
M_eff <- c(-1, -5, 1, 5) # Factor 1 main effects
N_eff <- c(-8, 4, -4, 8) # Factor 2 main effects

# we will need this a lot to create different Y matrices
empty_matrix <- matrix(NA,
                       nrow = length(M_eff),
                       ncol = length(N_eff))
```

Case 2 Demonstration of additive model

Let's start with the $m \times n$ treatment matrix Y and the main effects M and N :

```
# Create the treatment matrix Y under the additive model
# Each cell Y[i,j] is given by: G + M_eff[i] + N_eff[j]
Y_eff <- empty_matrix
for (i in 1:length(M_eff)) {
  for (j in 1:length(N_eff)) {
    Y_eff[i, j] <- M_eff[i] + N_eff[j]
  }
}

# For clarity, we also define the "reported" main
# effects with the global mean added:
M_mean <- G + M_eff # Treatment means for factor 1 (rows)
N_mean <- G + N_eff # Treatment means for factor 2 (columns)
# Y_mean is the same as Y_eff
Y_mean <- Y_eff + G

# Demonstrate that the additive model can be recovered from the
# reported main effects.
# Reconstruct Y_est using the additive assumption:
Y_est <- empty_matrix
for (i in 1:length(M_eff)) {
  for (j in 1:length(N_eff)) {
    Y_est[i, j] <- G + M_eff[i] + N_eff[j]
  }
}

# Verify that Y_est is identical to Y_mean:
identical(Y_est, Y_mean)
```

```
[1] TRUE
```

Case 1 Demonstration of what happens when there is an interaction

```
# Define an interaction effects matrix.
# We choose I_eff such that the sum over each row and each column
# is zero.
I_eff <- matrix(c(
  0, 1, 0, -1,
  0, -1, 0, 1,
  0, 1, 0, -1,
  0, -1, 0, 1
), nrow = length(M_eff), byrow = TRUE)

# Create the treatment matrix including interaction effects.
# Full model is now: Y_int = G + M_eff[i] + N_eff[j] + I_eff[i,j]
Y_int <- empty_matrix
for (i in 1:length(M_eff)) {
  for (j in 1:length(N_eff)) {
    Y_int[i, j] <- M_eff[i] + N_eff[j] + I_eff[i, j]
  }
}

# Recover the main effects from the treatment matrix with
# interactions. Because I_eff is defined to have zero
# mean by rows and columns, the recovered main effects will
# be the same as without interaction.
M_eff_int <- rowMeans(Y_int) - G # Factor 1: average over columns
N_eff_int <- colMeans(Y_int) - G # Factor 2: average over rows

# Reconstruct the treatment matrix from the recovered main effects
# (the additive part):
Y_int_est <- empty_matrix
for (i in 1:length(M_eff)) {
  for (j in 1:length(N_eff)) {
    Y_int_est[i, j] <- G + M_eff_int[i] + N_eff_int[j]
  }
}

# Compare the reconstructed (additive) treatment means to the
# actual treatment means.
# expect FALSE
identical(Y_int_est, Y_mean)
```

```
[1] FALSE
```

```

# But note: The full treatment means with interactions, Y_int, are different from Y_mean.
# The difference should be equal to interaction effects (I_eff)
# defined above:
I_recovered <- Y_int - Y_mean
print(I_recovered)

```

```

      [,1] [,2] [,3] [,4]
[1,] -25 -24 -25 -26
[2,] -25 -26 -25 -24
[3,] -25 -24 -25 -26
[4,] -25 -26 -25 -24

```

```

# expect I_recovered to be equal to I_eff
identical(I_recovered, I_eff)

```

```
[1] FALSE
```

Demonstration of Calculating treatment means from average of main effects

```

Y_est <- empty_matrix
for (i in 1:length(M_mean)) {
  for (j in 1:length(N_mean)) {
    Y_est[i, j] <- (M_mean[i] + N_mean[j]) / 2 #= mean(M[i], N[j])
  }
}

identical(Y_est, Y_mean)

```

```
[1] FALSE
```

```
Y_est - Y_mean
```

```

      [,1] [,2] [,3] [,4]
[1,]  4.5 -1.5  2.5 -3.5
[2,]  6.5  0.5  4.5 -1.5
[3,]  3.5 -2.5  1.5 -4.5
[4,]  1.5 -4.5 -0.5 -6.5

```